

A NEW SUBSPECIES OF *CONUS PENNACEUS* BORN, 1778 FROM SOUTH MOÇAMBIQUE

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Conus pennaceus Born, 1778 is a well known species, widely distributed throughout the Indian Ocean.

It is a highly variable species and in one locality we can find many forms, which will differ from each other in colour, pattern and general profile.

This variability has led some authors to describe as distinct species some of its forms, such as *C. praelatus* Hwass and *C. sindon* Reeve. Intergrades between these forms and typical specimens can be readily put forward.

The taxonomical rank of such taxa as *C. racemosus* Sowerby can also be discussed, but that is beyond the scope and purposes of the present paper.

It is noticeable that such a variable and well known species has not in the past given rise to the establishment of distinct subspecies. One can only infer from this that known forms were either sufficiently close to the typical one to enable identification or else sufficiently separated to suggest specific rank.

It happens that quite recently and through the efforts of Mrs ISABEL LEITÃO, a keen shell collector from Maputo, Moçambique, a new population was found which, while still identifiable as belonging to *C. pennaceus*, presents such consistent features as to warrant a subspecific treatment. The authors had the opportunity of examining a large number of specimens and therefore propose the following new taxon:

Conus pennaceus bazarutensis n. ssp.

Description:

Shell moderate in size, with a slightly convex profile and rounded shoulder. The spire is short and often gently concave towards the last whorls.

The body whorl presents many obsolete spiral cords, stronger on the anterior zone; some spiral striation is also present in the spire whorls, but can be seen only under magnification.

The anterior end is twisted over the columella. The aperture is rather wide, particularly along the anterior half of the shell.

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The protoconch is dirty white, whereas the post-nuclear whorls and the entire body whorl are grayish blue, covered with a complicated dark brown ornamentation which can form either a pattern of large bluish triangles bordered in brown, or a net of dark brown with small blue spots.

The aperture is of a deep violet hue, slightly lighter towards the interior of the shell; near the lip, the outer brown pattern shows through.

Holotype:

The holotype measures 46.4 x 25.8 mm. It was collected at Bazaruto Islands, a small archipelago close to the southern Moçambique coast, and is deposited in the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

Paratypes:

The following paratypes are designated:

1. 44.0 x 25.4 mm — New York Museum of Natural History
2. 50.2 x 28.9 mm — Col. César Fernandes, Cascais, Lisboa
3. 40.7 x 23.8 mm — Col. António Monteiro, Lisboa
4. 47.8 x 27.6 mm — Col. José Rosado, Maputo, Moçambique
5. 43.0 x 24.0 mm — Col. Amálio Ramalho

The type material and all other known specimens of the new subspecies were collected at Bazaruto Islands (21.° 40'S.).

Discussion:

The distribution of *C. pennaceus* along the coast of Moçambique, as can be gathered from extensive collecting during many years, is quite interesting.

As a matter of fact, its center of distribution seems to be the locality of Nacala. Many different forms occur together in an area that extends from Sunculo Point northwards until the mouth of Lúrio River; this is indeed a very restricted area, around 15.° S. latitude.

To the North of Lúrio River, *C. pennaceus* is still regularly found, but in only one rather constant form.

On the other hand, there are no registered occurrences of *C. pennaceus* to the South of Nacala area, except for the population now found at Bazaruto Islands.

That the present population can safely be included in the species *Conus pennaceus*, seems clear from the examination of its morphological features. But it is apparently restricted to a well defined geographical zone, on the southern border of the known distribution of the species.

On the other hand, the Bazaruto population does present a few characteristics that consistently separate it from its northern counterparts.

The most striking feature undoubtedly is the deep violet colour of the aperture. It should be recalled that in typical *C. pennaceus* and in all its hitherto known variations the aperture is always white.

The Bazaruto specimens also present a remarkably constant bluish ground colour and a pattern of small reticulations. Practically all the collected specimens were of comparatively small dimensions.

These characteristics justify the creation of the subspecies, as defined by MAYR (1979): "A subspecies is an aggregate of local populations of a species, inhabiting a geographic subdivision of the range of the species, and differing taxonomically from other populations of the species".

It should also be noted that the present subspecies must still be compared with another species, namely *C. lohri* Kilburn, 1972.

As a matter of fact, it can be safely ascertained that *C. lohri* is considerably close to *C. pennaceus* and other similar species, as judged from the observation of the living animal, which presents a very striking and similar coloration.

C. lohri has been reported from locations that lie further to the South than Bazaruto Islands. While most specimens are of a uniform colour, there are known instances in which a pattern of dark brown does appear, not only on the spire but also on the body whorl; moreover, all examined specimens present a "light violaceous, fading to flesh colour" aperture (KILBURN 1972).

But, when compared to the Bazaruto population of *C. pennaceus*, the specimens of *C. lohri* clearly have stockier shells, with straight sides and swollen shoulders; all specimens of *C. lohri* that the authors were able to study had pink protoconches.

Aknowledgements:

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RESUMO

Os autores descrevem uma nova subespécie do género *Conus*, do Sul de Moçambique.

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A

A'

B

B'

A, A' — *Conus pennaceus bazarutensis* n. ssp. Holotype

B, B' — *Conus pennaceus bazarutensis* n. ssp. Paratype 3